

YOUR CAR IS IN YOUR SMART MOBILE PHONE

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ABSTRACT: Due to the fact that the summer season lasts for a period of 6 months, starting from May and continuing until October, during this period, temperatures rise to the limits of 50 degrees Celsius, which in turn causes many problems. For motorists, this temperature negatively affects the security of the car, as heat retention inside the car leads to the emission of toxic gases that are not noticed by drivers. Also, there are some things that, if exposed to high temperature, may explode and that some overlook, such as batteries, gas lighters, perfume bottles, sterilizers, and so on. But as it has been said that as long as the damage does not affect humans, there is no harm in that, but contrary to what we expect, the high temperature of the car causes health damage such as suffocation, which leads to death in some cases. It has also been proven in some research that high temperatures can cause cancerous diseases. Increasing temperatures may produce toxic gases in the car that harm the user and its components, even causing loss of life and the car. The car is a valuable thing that can be stolen, and the lack of knowledge of the car owner of the user of his car and its location is an interesting problem. Keeping pace with the development in the world of technology, we have decided to implement a project that represents a link between the car and its owner through the smart phone application. The information that the car owner gets about his vehicle is of high importance because it protects him from many problems that may occur in the car and harm the car and the passenger. This information includes the temperatures inside the car, the leakage of dangerous gases, information about whether there is a person inside the car, and the location of the car using IoT sensors. It is possible for the driver to observe this information inside the car in a conventional manner, or he may even not notice this information. Therefore, storing this information in a database and sending it to the car owner in the mobile application is an easy way to find out this information, especially when he is away from the car. These days the human world spends a lot of time and need from the car. It is considered the friend of the roads and the most popular means of transportation from one place to another. The more important the object is; the more attention it needs to be given. Therefore, in this project, we are looking forward to focusing on caring for the car and communicating with it intelligently in light of the spread of smart technologies. During these days, the rapid spread and expansion of technology gives us the opportunity to innovate and come up with solutions that benefit life. In this project, we will activate the Internet of things (IoT) in the car and connect it to the device closest to human, which is the smartphone.

Key words: Smart Car, Internet of things (IoT), Mobile App.